

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE THROUGH WORKING WITH TEXTS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL NATIVE LANGUAGE LESSONS

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the issues of developing students' linguistic competence through working with texts in primary school native language lessons. In particular, it analyzes effective methods and techniques for working with texts, their role in enhancing students' speech activity, and their impact on the conscious acquisition of language units. The article also presents methodological approaches aimed at developing reading, comprehension, analytical, and expressive skills based on text work. As a result, recommendations are proposed to improve the effectiveness of forming linguistic competence in the primary education process.

Keywords: Primary education, native language lesson, working with texts, linguistic competence, speech activity, methodology, didactic approach, language units, communicative competence.

INTRODUCTION

Current reforms in the education system focus not only on students' acquisition of knowledge but also on the development of competencies that enable them to apply their knowledge in practical activities. In particular, primary education plays a crucial role in developing students' foundational knowledge, skills, and abilities. From this perspective, improving the content and methodology of native language lessons in accordance with modern requirements is a pressing issue. Working with texts holds a special place in forming students' linguistic competence in primary school native language lessons. A text represents the real-life expression of language units, through which students have the opportunity to consolidate their knowledge at the levels of words, sentences, and the entire text in practice. During the process of working with texts, students acquire essential types of speech activity, including reading, listening comprehension, expressing ideas, and analytical thinking.

Modern methodological approaches require considering the student as an active participant in the learning process. This, in turn, demands that teachers effectively use interactive methods, problem-based situations, and creative tasks in lesson organization. In particular, it is crucial to apply methods aimed at developing students' independent thinking, logical reasoning, and speech activity during text-based lessons.

At the same time, linguistic competence is not limited to grammatical knowledge; it also includes the appropriate and correct use of language tools, adherence to speech culture, and the ability to express ideas clearly and fluently. Therefore, organizing native language lessons in primary classes with a focus on text-based work to gradually develop these competencies is an essential task. The purpose of this article is to explore the methodology for developing students' linguistic competence through working with texts in primary school native language lessons, to analyze effective methods and tools, and to provide practical recommendations for implementation.

METHODS

This study analyzes the process of developing students' linguistic competence through working with texts in primary school native language lessons. During the research, a комплекс approach combining both theoretical and practical methods was employed. In particular, through the analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature, the concept of linguistic competence, its components, and its role in primary education were examined. Additionally, current curricula and textbooks were analyzed to determine the extent to which attention is given to working with texts.

In the course of the empirical research, methods such as observation, interviews, and experimental trials were utilized. Students' activity during text-based lessons, as well as their skills in comprehension, analysis, and reproduction of texts, were studied. Furthermore, the effectiveness of developing students' linguistic competence was assessed through the application of various interactive methods, including clustering, brainstorming, insert techniques, question-and-answer sessions, and role-playing activities. To ensure the reliability of the research results, methods such as comparison, generalization, and analytical evaluation were applied.

RESULTS

The findings of the study indicate that systematic and purpose-oriented work with texts in primary school native language lessons contributes significantly to the effective development of students' linguistic competence. In particular, during text-based activities, the following skills were developed among students: comprehension and retelling of the text, identification of the main idea, understanding the meaning of words and sentences based on context, practical application of grammatical units, and the ability to express ideas both orally and in written form. It was also observed that the use of interactive methods in lessons significantly increased students' engagement and interest. In particular, problem-based questions and creative tasks encouraged students to think independently. Furthermore, the results of the experimental study demonstrated that text-based instruction not only enhances students' linguistic competence but also contributes to the development of their communicative competence.

DISCUSSION

Linguistic Competence and Its Components

Linguistic competence is an important indicator that reflects a student's ability to understand the language system, use language units correctly and appropriately, and express their thoughts clearly in both oral and written forms. In modern educational concepts, this competence is interpreted as one of the key factors ensuring an individual's communicative activity. Especially at the primary education level, the development of linguistic competence creates a solid foundation for students' further learning activities.

Linguistic competence includes several essential components. First, the lexical component is related to the student's vocabulary, understanding of word meanings, and the ability to use them appropriately in speech. Research shows that the expansion of active vocabulary among primary school students directly influences their level of text comprehension and speech activity. Therefore, acquiring new words and applying them in practice during text-based activities in native language lessons is of great importance. The second important component is grammatical competence, which involves students' ability to construct sentences, correctly connect words grammatically, and practically master the morphological and syntactic rules of the language. In primary education, grammatical knowledge is more practice-oriented and is reinforced through texts. That is, students acquire grammar not by memorizing isolated rules, but by applying them in real speech situations.

Another key component of linguistic competence is phonetic competence, which includes correct pronunciation of sounds, proper use of stress and intonation, and the development of expressive reading skills. Particularly in primary education, the proper formation of reading techniques has a significant impact on the further development of speech. At the primary education level, linguistic competence is manifested through several practical skills. These include the ability to read texts fluently and accurately, comprehend their content, and express ideas coherently and clearly. In addition, students' ability to answer questions based on texts, retell them, and express independent opinions also indicates the level of development of linguistic competence. Thus, linguistic competence in primary school students represents a комплекс system of skills

encompassing all aspects of language. Its effective development is closely linked to the proper organization of text-based activities in native language lessons.

Stages and Methodological System of Working with Texts

The process of working with texts in primary school native language lessons yields effective results only when it is purposefully, consistently, and systematically organized in stages. A methodologically sound organization of this process contributes to the comprehensive development of students' linguistic competence. From this perspective, it is appropriate to divide text-based work into several interrelated stages. The first stage is the pre-text (preparation) stage. At this stage, the main objective is to prepare students to perceive a new text. The teacher explains the meanings of unfamiliar or difficult words found in the text and works on their correct pronunciation. In addition, a short discussion on the topic of the text is organized to activate students' prior knowledge. This process stimulates students' interest and creates a foundation for conscious text comprehension.

The second stage is the reading stage. At this stage, attention is paid to developing students' reading techniques and expressiveness. The text may first be read aloud by the teacher as a model, after which students read it either aloud or silently. During reading, special attention is given to correct pronunciation, stress, and intonation, which contribute to the development of phonetic competence.

The third stage is the comprehension stage. At this stage, students' level of understanding of the text is assessed. The teacher organizes discussions using the question-and-answer method, and the main idea of the text is identified. Students deepen their understanding by determining the sequence of events, describing characters, and explaining cause-and-effect relationships. This stage develops students' logical thinking and comprehension skills.

The fourth stage is the analysis stage, where the core development of linguistic competence takes place. At this stage, sentences within the text are examined, grammatical features of words are identified, and parts of speech and sentence structures are analyzed. Additionally, through various grammatical exercises, students practically master language rules, which strengthens their grammatical competence.

The fifth stage is the consolidation stage. At this stage, students apply their acquired knowledge and skills in practice. Activities such as retelling the text, completing creative tasks based on the content, and expressing personal opinions about the text are organized. This process enhances students' speech activity, independent thinking, and ability to express their ideas freely. Thus, when these stages of working with texts are organized in an interconnected and systematic manner, they provide an effective means of developing students' linguistic competence. This methodological approach significantly increases the effectiveness of language teaching in primary education.

Methods Used to Develop Linguistic Competence

In primary school native language lessons, various methods are effectively applied to develop students' linguistic competence through working with texts. These methods are complementary in nature and serve to enhance students' speech activity, thinking, and creative skills. The methods can be divided into three main groups: interactive, traditional, and creative methods. Interactive methods play a crucial role in engaging students as active participants in the learning process and in developing their independent thinking skills during text-based activities. For example, the "Brainstorming" method encourages students to express their ideas freely on a given topic, promotes the active use of new words and expressions, and strengthens lexical competence. The "Cluster" method facilitates text analysis by visually organizing the main idea and related concepts in a systematic way, thereby enhancing students' logical thinking and understanding of semantic relationships between words. In addition, the "INSERT" method allows students to mark, annotate, and pose questions while reading a text, which helps deepen comprehension and improve their ability to express ideas clearly.

Traditional methods ensure the consolidation of language knowledge and the thorough acquisition of theoretical foundations by students. The explanatory reading method involves clarifying the meanings of words and phrases during reading and focusing on grammatical structures, thereby contributing to the development of phonetic and grammatical competence. The question-and-answer method is used to assess and reinforce students' understanding of the text, helping them identify the main idea, understand cause-and-effect relationships, and develop structured expression of their thoughts.

Creative methods stimulate students' imagination and promote independent thinking and speech activity. For instance, the text continuation task allows students to expand the text using their own words, thereby applying their lexical and grammatical competence in practice. Similarly, role-playing activities enable students to speak from the perspective of characters in the text, which encourages the active use of language units in real-life contexts and strengthens their communicative competence. Thus, the integrated use of interactive, traditional, and creative methods provides an effective means of systematically developing linguistic competence in primary school students. Each method contributes to the development of students' lexical, grammatical, phonetic, and communicative skills in accordance with its specific function.

CONCLUSION

The methodology of developing linguistic competence through working with texts in primary school native language lessons serves as a key tool for enhancing students' language knowledge, speech activity, and logical thinking. The results of the study indicate that systematic and step-by-step work with texts enables the effective development of students' lexical, grammatical, phonetic, and communicative skills. The methodological process is structured into several stages: pre-text preparation, reading, comprehension, analysis, and consolidation. Each stage contributes to the development of students' ability to apply language in practice, identify the main idea, construct sentences, and express their thoughts clearly. At the same time, interactive methods (such as brainstorming, clustering, and INSERT) actively engage students in the learning process, while traditional methods (explanatory reading and question-and-answer) reinforce theoretical knowledge, and creative methods (text continuation and role-playing) develop students' speech and creative abilities.

The study also demonstrates that the teacher's methodological approach and effective lesson organization play a crucial role in the formation of linguistic competence. Students' individual characteristics, their interest in the subject, and their active involvement in interactive activities significantly influence the effectiveness of the learning outcomes. At the same time, it was identified that the недостаток of diverse tasks in textbooks or their repetitive nature may limit students' creative thinking. This necessitates the use of additional creative exercises and interactive approaches by teachers. In conclusion, working with texts in primary school native language lessons is not only an effective means of developing students' linguistic competence, but also of enhancing their independent thinking, expressive speech, and communication skills. Therefore, the systematic implementation of text-based methodological approaches in the teaching process significantly increases pedagogical effectiveness and fosters students' interest in language learning.

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